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ARTS

THE ROLE OF FEMALE SCULPTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AZERBAIJANI ART

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the importance of using historical architectural monuments - Karabakh monuments in the formation of patriotic education of young people. It is known to everyone that for nearly 30 years, 20% of the territory of Azerbaijan and its historical architectural monuments were occupied by Armenian usurpers. In order to teach the youth to love the motherland, we need to arm them with knowledge about our valuable resources there. At the same time, by studying the history of Karabakh monuments, we get to know the national culture of our ancestors. It should be noted that although most of the architectural pearls located in different regions of Azerbaijan have come down to our time, those related to Karabakh have been subjected to considerable destruction from time to time, especially in the last thirty years, as a result of Armenian aggression, and many of them have been appropriated by them. Among them, there are Christian-type religious architectural monuments from the period of ancient Caucasian Albania and the Early Middle Ages. In the middle Ages, numerous civil buildings were built in different corners of Karabakh along with mosques, tombs and castles. Among them, the buildings created by the architect Karbalayi Safikhhan Karabakhi stand out. Of course, since these buildings with the Karabakh address are directly related to the local people living here due to their shape, masonry technology and aesthetic capacity, it is impossible to hide their real address - who owns them. On the other hand, the fact that the Armenians who erected a monument in Agara district in honor of the 150th anniversary of their resettlement from Iran to Karabakh in 1978 is only regrettable and laughable...Our purpose is to past this to young people.

Keywords: Sculpture, Woman, Bust, Portrait, Creativity, Art.

Current research on the history of sculpture, which is a type of fine art, proves that the roots and origins of this art are related to human labor, spiritual beliefs, and aesthetic imagination during the period of primitive community structure. The first examples of sculpture, consisting of animal and human images and reliefs, create a clear idea of the inner world of primitive man, his belief in the forces of nature, and his worldview. As a result of archaeological excavations conducted in several countries of the world, various examples of sculptures from the ancient stone age have been found. During the archaeological excavations conducted in the territory of Azerbaijan, rare sculptural works were discovered, which provide rich information about the culture, art, and outlook of the tribes engaged in agriculture and cattle breeding.

According to its origin, Azerbaijani sculpture is connected to many historical and artistic creative traditions, the roots of which go back to the Gobustan tribes of the Middle Stone Age. Therefore, researchers consider the Middle Stone Age to be the oldest stage of our fine art. These are images of animals, people and boats drawn on rocks by ancient people who lived in Gobustan. The reliefs created on the Absheron rock paintings are among the first sculptural works.

The analysis of the general picture of Azerbaijani sculpture from ancient times to the 20th century shows that our plastic art has always existed, and all its types and genres have progressed, despite the fact that development has been replaced by decline and crisis in a number of cases. Although sculpture underwent changes in form and content in the Middle Ages, this

art as a whole did not remain under development and enriched our cultural history with new examples of art. Azerbaijani sculpture has already entered the 20th century with its own characteristic features, which have many centuries of history, great traditions and rich means of artistic representation.

It would be historical injustice to deny the rapid development of sculpture in the period after the 20s and the role of artists invited to our republic in this field, while acknowledging the disasters and tribulations caused by the Bolshevik invasion and Soviet rule to the Azerbaijani people. However, attributing the first professional Azerbaijani sculpture of the 20th century to the name of only invited sculptors should be considered at least as indifference, indifference and disrespect to our national art.

The creativity of female sculptors played its own role in the creation and formation of both professional sculpture and a large collective of sculptors in Azerbaijan.

I mainly want to provide information about the creativity of prominent female sculptors of Azerbaijan

Zivar Mammadova, the first female sculptor of Azerbaijan, was born in an intellectual family in Baku. During her studies at the Baku art school, in 1920-1924, she had creative relations with such talented teachers as Erziya, Y.I. Keylixis, E.S. Samorodov, and A.I. Kosichkin. Even in his student years, he was engaged in independent creativity, created various busts, sculptures and figures. Zivar Mammadova, who started her freelance career by creating the busts of the famous

Azerbaijani wrestler "Sali-Suleyman", the people's artist "H. Sarabiski", later created the portrait of the Azer-

bajani poetess Mehsati Ganjavi, illustrations of Nizami's works, "Eagle" placed on the steep slope, etc. sculptures are made.

Pic.1

By performing the portrait of the People's Artist "H. Sarabiski" in a more attractive manner, Zivar Mammadova managed to reveal the important and "extended" aspects of the actor's inner world.

During the war and post-war years, Zivar Mammadova continued her independent creative pursuits. Working in the field of portraits, he painted war heroes "Huseynbala Aliyev", "Idris Suleymanov", "Geray Asadov", oilman "Baba Pirmammadin", artist "A. Azimzade", folk poet "Mammad Rahim" and others. creates busts.

Giving an artistic appearance to people who are strong and courageous in life and work runs through Zivar Mammadova's creativity like a red line. Zivar Mammadova has created busts of our oil workers since she was still a student. His portrait "Oilman Baba Pirmammadin" and the composition "Grape picking women" are among such works.

When paying attention to the portrait gallery created by Zivar Mammadova, no one doubts that they are directly related to creative people. This can be clearly seen in the portrait of "Mommeh Rahim".

Starting from the first days of the Second World War, Z. Mammadova actively began to create images of heroic fighters. Huseynbala Aliyev's portrait attracts the viewer with its bright characteristic, great power of generalization. In the portrait of "Idris Suleymanov", he tries to show his courage, invincibility and belief in victory.

The image of "Azim Azimzade" was made by the sculptor from living nature. Later, this statue was

erected on the artist's grave. Z. Mammadova tries to show the responsible role of artists in this image. A. Azimzade's portrait is distinguished by the conciseness and clarity of the plastic forms.

Zivar Mammadova tried to show the best aspects of her heroes, that is why the characters she created are carriers of different, deeply individual, true human qualities.

The work on the portrait of the famous Azerbaijani composer "Uzeyir Hajibeyov" is an important stage in Z. Mammadova's creativity. This work is placed in the lobby of the Azerbaijan State Conservatory. Sculptor Zivar khanum notes that "I created the image of the composer from living nature.

Professor Tokay Mammadov, the son of Zivar Mammadova, a folk artist, erected a monumental monument to the composer Uzeyir Hajibeyov in front of the building of the Azerbaijan State Conservatory in Baku in 1960. Tokay Mammadov started preparing the initial sketches of Uzeyir Bey's monument in 1957. The sculptor approached the work on the monument in a prepared manner. It seems that she continued the work started by her mother, Zivar Mammadova, the first female sculptor of Azerbaijan.

Zivar Mammadova embodied the best features and sublime feelings of her contemporaries in the female portraits she created. The artist managed to accurately show the highest qualities characteristic of Azerbaijani women - their sincerity, self-confidence, delicacy, and inner beauty. The cotton weaver "Basti Bagirova", the first female aviator "Leyla Mammadbeyova", the carpet

weaver "Sona Ahmadova" are his heroes that he immortalized on stone.

Zivar Mammadova also has great experience in creating decorative figurines that decorate the home. His small sculptures depicting the characters of "Dancer" and "Cotton Woman" made of porcelain in exquisite taste are interesting.

In the works of Zivar Mammadova, figurines are attractive in terms of volume integrity, plastic, dynamic, transitions are soft and fluid, and colors are delicately processed. In addition to the works mentioned above, his small-sized sculptures depicting the characters of U. Hajibeyov's operettas are also interesting. Due to these qualities, the sculptor's porcelain works "Dancer girl" and "Girl with a doll" were successfully exhibited at the exhibition of Azerbaijani artists organized in 1957.

Hayat Abdullayeva was born in 1912 in the city of Darband, in 1950 she graduated from the Leningrad Institute of Painting, Sculpture and Architecture named after Repin.

Pic.2

The decorative nature of the figures, the dynamism of the compositions and the plastic expression of the images attracted the attention of the sculptors who benefited from H. Abdullayeva's works. In general, the work "Seven Beauties" can be considered a significant success of H. Abdillayeva in the field of small decorative plastic.

In the 1950s, H. Abdullayeva worked very effectively in the genre of small-form plastic. The charged image of Mashadi Ibad and the image of Khala in the operetta "Arshin Mal Alan" mixed with sincere humor revealed the decorative talent of the sculptor.

Dahi Nizami's works based on "Seven Beauties", as well as small-sized porcelain figurines such as "Talysh girl", "Gabetokhuyan girl", "Woman with child" are the first works that define the future creative perspective of the author.

Hayat Abdullayeva, who has worked on easel and decorative forms of sculpture and has created a number of valuable composition groups and small figurines, has a special tendency towards lyrical themes. The sculptor, who glorified mother's love in the compositions "Motherhood" (1953) and "Lay-Lay" (1963), dedicated his two-figure work "Youth" (1964) to young lovers. In this poetic work carved from wood, the image of a boy and a girl watching the world of love, dreams and dreams head to head is also very impressive. Among the author's works, the sculpture "Hajar" (1959), the colorful decorative sculptures (1955) that enliven the characters of Nizami's poem "Seven Beauties" are also famous.

Hayat Abdullayeva's seven beautiful figurines are original, artistic-aesthetic essence, volume, color, light, etc. it meets all the requirements of modern plastic in the sense of correctly finding the degree of proportionality.

The theme of H. Abdullayeva's works "Portrait of a Girl" (1966), "Spring" (1961), "Youth" (1964) was taken from modern life.

When you pay attention to the work "Portrait of a Girl" (1966), how much love, freedom, purity, tenderness you feel.

Hayat Abdullayeva's works "Lullaby" made of aluminum, "Youth" made of walnut wood, "Hajar on horseback" are exhibited in the National Art Museum of Azerbaijan.

Hayat Abdullayeva's work "Game" is interesting in terms of composition. A pensive girl is depicted in front of a chess game.

In the composition "Motherhood", Hayat Abdullayeva tried to achieve full understanding by describing the figure of mother and child in space.

In 1956-57, Hayat Abdullayeva worked on the portraits "Vagif" (Shusha city, Cidir plain) and "Nizami". In these works, one can feel the hand of a master craftsman, who is able to feel the material, to give the described a complete composite character. Vagif's portrait attracts attention with its fresh plasticity, inspiration, and poetics of the appearance, while the image of Nizami Ganjavi attracts attention with its delicate lyricism and rich shades of emotions.

The portrait "Hajar" (1959) is distinguished by the size and plastic integrity of its composition. He was created while galloping on a horse. The sharpness of the movement is excellently executed.

After 1960, Hayat Abdullayeva began to create characteristic lines, expressive psychologically rich images in women's portraits. We can clearly see such qualities in the portrait of fellow artist Vajiha Samadova.

The constant development and improvement of Azerbaijani plastic makes it take a leading position in the visual arts of the republic

Sudaba Aliyeva was born in 1927, graduated from the Art School in 1952, graduated from the Leningrad Higher Art School in 1958 and returned to Bakli

Since then, he has been creating works of art independently. He contributes to the art of Azerbaijan with "Shepherd", "Bust of Niyazi", "Bust of J. Mammadguluzade", "Statue of H.B. Zardabi", "Cocoon Girl" and other works.

The "Shepherd" sculpture stands out for its composition, integrity and perfection of form, plasticity and vitality.

Sudaba Aliverdibeyova's bust of "Niyazi" reflects deep philosophical ideas. The sculptor, who was closely acquainted with the People's Artist of Azerbaijan, composer and conductor Niyazi, was fully familiar with his work. For this reason, the artist made a portrait of the conductor for the first time after searching for a long time.

The "Mother" monument dedicated to the memory of those who died in the battles against fascism in 1941-1945 in Sahil settlement of Baku attracts more attention with its monumentality. The mother statue is proud,

strong-willed and indomitable. A mother who sacrificed her children for the freedom of her country is ready to endure all the hardships of life in this situation.

This image gave the sculptor a wide opportunity to pay tribute to the memory of all the soldiers who made sacrifices during the years of the Great Patriotic War, to show once again the feelings of anger and hatred against the war with full sharpness, and to illustrate the fact that the bloody war years led to terrible human tragedies.

Apart from these, the sculptor's works such as "Nepali woman", "Mahsati Ganjavi", "Airplane girl", and "Hope" also brought him success. The statue of genius Uzeyir Hajibeyli occupies a special place in the gallery of these works.

The main works of art are "Portrait of Niyazi", "Sahengli girl", "Jalil Mammadguluzade", "Portrait of a girl", "Hasan bey Zardabi", "Huseyn Javid" and others. He was an active participant in national and international exhibitions.

The works of Sudaba Aliverdibeyova are currently decorating the cities and regions of our republic. The bust of J. Mammadguluzade, created by his hands, occupies a special place among the busts in the lobby of the National Drama Theater. The majestic statue of H.B. Zardabi is among the statues that decorate the facade of the National Library named after M.F. Akhundzade. The portrait of H.Javid in the home museum, the bust of Niyazi in the home museum, and the woodcut "Cocoon Girl" in the National Museum of Art are the products of Ms. Sudaba's work.

Elmira Huseynova graduated from Azim Azimzade Azerbaijan State Art School (1954) and IY Repin Leningrad Institute of Painting, Sculpture and Architecture (1960). His works are distinguished by an interesting artistic solution to the subject, his sculptures attract attention with their unique shape and memorable form findings. With the exception of one or two works that he worked on after his student years, none of his works repeat each other either in composition, plastic solution, or form. From work to work, we witness that his lines are improved, compositions are enriched with details that complement the various emotions and thoughts that individualize the images.

Pic.3 Elmira Huseynova's first successful work is a wooden copy of "Kolkhozchu woman" (1957).

Elmira Huseynova shows special inclination towards family, love and happiness topics. One of the themes addressed by the sculptor is the mother theme. Her works that reflect her mother's love, mother's joy, mother's care, sublime mother's feeling are examples of art that instill sincere feelings. In the works "Family", "Motherhood", "My family", "Happiness" and others, which were used in various materials, we see an expressive and memorable solution to this content.

The work "Motherhood" (1967) carved from stone is one of the most successful works of the sculptor. It depicts a mother with her head turned forward and her sweet baby falling asleep hugging her head.

Another work from the series "Motherhood" is the work "Happiness" made of wood. The child is tightly sheltered by the mother. The mother's eyes are focused on a mysterious world.

Elmira Huseynova tests a topic in several materials and chooses the most successful one. External similarity was not the main thing for him. He tried to give this similarity with the feelings that exist in the depths of the human heart and did not miss even the small features of the character, and thus the whole meaning intonation of the work was focused on reviving the inner creative sublimity in the creative and contemplative moments of a person.

Elmira Huseynova's "Collective Farmer Woman", "Worker", "Family", "C. Jabbarli", "Mother", "Rasul Reza" and others. His works are distinguished by the compactness of their plastic forms and the originality of their compositions.

Elmira Huseynova also showed herself in the field of monumental sculpture - the statue of J. Jabbarli in Sumgait (1966), the statue of H. Zardabi in Baku (1983).

In her work, our genius artist Elmira Huseynova saw J. Jabbarli as a talented person, an ardent patriot, and a person who bravely intervened in life events and engraved it on the material. The portrait of the famous poet is depicted as a bas-relief

Monuments placed on the graves of fellow scientist U. Hajibeyov, Bulbul, J. Jabbarli, and C. Mammadguluzade show the best aspects of architectural sculpture. These monuments attract the viewer with their simplicity, depth of images and execution skill.

Elmira Huseynova managed to skillfully make the portrait of "Togrul Narambayov", the portrait of "Student", and the portraits of "Rasul Rza" from wood.

E. Huseynova, who created the portrait of "Sattar Bahlulzade" in 1965, managed to attract attention with her interesting image of the artist. If the other author of the work of the same name, Omer Eldarov, absorbed the lyrics that make up the artist's creativity into the image he created, E. Huseynova, on the other hand, brought to the fore the integrity, determination and conventionality characteristic of S. Bahlulzade's existence. Portraits of folk poet, Hero of Socialist Labor Rasul Rza (1970) and cotton master, Hero of Socialist Labor Gudrat Samadov (1972) are also distinguished by their uniqueness. In these works, for the first time in Azerbaijani sculpture, the author included logical attributes in portrait compositions that enrich the images and reveal their inner world.

The tense moments of the human character and his feelings are revealed in the portrait of the sculptor "The Artist's Family". By showing different age limits, the rhythmic lines are aimed at describing the unity and interconnectedness of the family.

One of the works that attracted the attention of Elmira Huseynova was the monument of "Hasanbey Zardabi". This work is considered one of the last works of the artist. The bronze monument of Hasanbey Zardabi, the founder of the democratic press of Azerbaijan, was placed in the inner city.

Munavvar Rzayeva was born in 1929. In 1950, he graduated from the art school named after A. Azimzade, and in 1956, he graduated from the Moscow State Art Academy named after V. I. Surikov, from the sculpture department. He was a student of the famous sculptor Nikolai Tomsky. Since 1953, he has been accepted as a member of the Union of Artists and since then has participated in various republican general union and international exhibitions.

His works, which have absorbed the warmth of his hands and are the embodiment of the sense of professionalism and beauty, are stored in the State Museum of Art of Azerbaijan named after R. Mustafayev, the Museum of Literature named after Nizami of ANAS, the house-museum of M.S. Ordubadi, the Siyazan Culture House, the Art Fund.

In 1953, he participated for the first time in the II republican exhibition with the work "Alpinist girl".

M. Rzayeva was a sculptor with a unique handwriting and was distinguished mainly by being a master of psychological portraits; In order to reflect the inner world of the images he created, he used the eyes of the portrait with special delicacy and skill.

Pic. 4

If we characterize his creativity, the image of Mikayil Mushfig should be mentioned among his most known and loved works.

Sevil Gaziyeva is one of the labor heroes of the 70s, and her tragic fate melted the heart of Mrs. Munavvar, and the artist created the image of this hard-working, masculine zealous girl. In 1969, the image of S. Ghaziyeva, the first mechanic woman in Azerbaijan, was placed in the garden on Bakikhanov Street. Sevil is like a winged bird: its hair and beak make its flight more effective and dynamic.

In this work, which is a clear example of M. Rzayeva's handwriting, Sevil, the heroic daughter of Mil duzun, unites her triumphant, triumphant views with her poetic inner world. Another work of the famous sculptor Munavvar Rzayeva, the image of "Ayna Sultanova" attracts everyone's attention. The granite bust of Ayna Sultanova, a state and party figure of the Soviet era, one of the victims of the system she established, erected in 1986 on Atatürk Avenue, is characterized by the fullness of the image.

One of Munavvar Khanum's famous works in Ganja is the monument to the poetess Nigar Rafibeyli: the poetess sits in the greenery and looks into the distance. In the image of Nigar khanum, the only daughter of Khudadat bey Rafibeyli, who was the minister of health during the years of the republic, and then the governor of Ganja, who was shot without a trial by the Bolsheviks, the sculptor was able to reveal the contradictions of life.

Munavvar's favorite work was the image of Mahsati. The artist depicted him sitting on the ground. Mahsati, whose hands are tied to her neck for her beautiful performance in the war, holds her head high as if she is looking into the future.

Bahmanyar, Hasan Bey Zardabi, Mirza Alakbar Sabir, Imaduddin Nasimi. The images of Mammad Said Ordubadi, Shah Ismayil Khatai, Huseyn Javid... are works with a special position in his creativity.

His last work - the image of Sadigjan - the "Father of Azerbaijani Tar", which has been confirmed by his artistry, reflects one of the sculptor's great hopes and

dreams, which did not come true - the desire to expel this work to his ancestral homeland Shusha.

Munavvar Rzayeva's latest work is located on a mountain located in the Gusar region of Azerbaijan at 3763 m. A bronze bas-relief of Azerbaijan's national leader Heydar Aliyev (length 82 cm, width 59 cm, weight 35 kg) was attached to the "Heydar Peak". The bas-relief was attached to the highest mountain peak conquered by a group of climbers on May 10, 1998, on the occasion of Heydar Aliyev's 75th anniversary.

As a result, it can be noted that the creativity of women artists has had its place in the development of Azerbaijani art and continues to do so.

Thus, the diverse creations of female sculptors of Azerbaijan can be classified as follows:

All areas of our sculpture (monumental and easel, memorial, relief and small sculpture) are reflected in the work of female sculptors of Azerbaijan.

The portrait works created by each of our female sculptors attract attention with their philosophical qualities. The dominant method in the creativity of our female sculptors is realism

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BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

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ON THE NUMBER OF SOME FISH SPECIES CAUGHT IN THE AYDAR-ARNASOY LAKE SYSTEM

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Abstract

The article provides information on the number and monitoring of the current state of commercial fish in the Tuzkan, East Arnasoy, and Aidar lakes of the Aidar-Arnasoy lake system, carried out during the summer and autumn seasons of 2019. 352 specimens of 5 fish species were collected from Tuzkan Lake, 556 specimens of 5 fish species from East Arnasoy Lake, and 379 specimens of 4 fish species from Aidar Lake. Control hunting was carried out during the stages of lowering and lifting a total of 48 fishing nets (average 25 nets).

Аннотация

В статье представлена информация о количестве и мониторинге текущего состояния промысловых рыб в озерах Тузкан, Восточный Арнасой и Айдар озерной системы Айдар-Арнасой, проведенных в течение летнего и осеннего сезонов 2019 года. Из озера Тузкан было собрано 352 экземпляров 5 видов рыб, из озера Восточный Арнасой – 556 экземпляров 5 видов рыб, из озера Айдар – 379 экземпляров 4 видов рыб. Контрольная охота проводилась на этапах опускания и подъема в общей сложности 48 рыболовных сетей (в среднем 25 сетей).

Keywords: fish species, ААКТ, nets, quantities, monitoring, commercial fish, accounting.

Ключевые слова: виды рыб, ААКТ, сети, количества, мониторинг, промысловый рыб, учет.

Введение. На сегодняшний день в глобальном масштабе уделяется особое внимание вопросу продовольствия. В том числе, следует отдельно отметить качественные и количественные показатели рыбы и рыбопродуктов. В Узбекистане в этом направлении также проводятся большое количество мероприятий, включая процессы цифровизации. Поэтому, в целях определения численности и количественных показателей видов рыб в существующих реках и естественных озерах нашей республики, их рационального их использования, про-

водятся большое количество научно-практических работ. Это, в свою очередь, считается одним из наиболее актуальной задачей на современном этапе стремительного развития общества. В связи с этим, сотрудники Института Зоологии Академии наук Республики Узбекистан совместно с сотрудниками Государственного унитарного предприятия системы озер Айдар-Арнасой, летом 2019 года (30.07 – 3.08.2019 г.) и осенью (24.09 – 28.09.2019 г.) провели мониторинг текущего состояния рыб в системе озер Айдар-Арнасой. Результатом этих наблюдений стали контрольные отловы на озерах

Айдар, Арнасой и Тузкан озерной системы Айдар-Арнасой, а также проведены работы по их учёту.

Материалы и методы исследования. При этом использовались рыболовные сети с размерами ячейки от 28 мм до 65 мм, длиной от 60 м до 70 м, шириной от 3 м до 10 м. Все проведенные контрольные отловы проводились в виде забрасывания сетей в назначенный район во второй половине дня и сбора отлова из сетей во второй половине дня. Работа по подсчету, измерению длины и веса выловленных образцов рыбы проводилась на побережье или в пунктах сбора рыбы. Ниже в таблицах 1, 2, 3 можно ознакомиться с видами выловленных рыб, их количеству, показателями размеров, длиной рыболовных сетей, их шириной, расстоянием между ячейками и различными аналогичными параметрами.

Определение параметров образцов рыбы и камерная обработка проводились на основе общепринятых методик [1]. Датировка и вычислительная работа были выполнены с помощью компьютерных приложений и использованием данных биологической статистики (Microsoft excel, 2019) [1].

Полученные результаты. Ячейки для рыболовных сетей системы озер Айдар-Арнасой на озере Тузкан имели размер от 32 мм до 65 мм, длину от 60 м до 70 м, ширину от 3 м до 10 м, с общим количеством от 20 до 50 сетей (в каждой комбинации) из шелка и искусственных волокон. В результате 16 разового забрасывания и сбора сетей от 0,1 км до 2 км от берега на глубину от 3 м до 15 м, были подсчитаны 120 образцов судака обыкновенного (*Sander lucioperca*), длиной от 18 см до 48 см, весом от 100 гр до 2000 гр; 13 образцов серебряного карася (*Carassius gibelio*) длиной от 16 см до 32,5 см, весом от 200 г до 500 г; 214 образцов аральской плотвы (*Rutilus aralensis*) длиной от 18 см до 25 см, весом от 200 гр до 300 гр; 4 образца карпа обыкновенного (*Cyprinus carpio*) длиной от 18 см

до 45 см, весом от 200 гр до 900 гр и 1 образец Жереха аральского (*Aspius aspius iblioides*) длиной 20 см, весом 220 гр (таблица 1).

Ячейки для рыболовных сетей системы озер Айдар-Арнасой на озере Восточный Арнасай имели размер от 28 мм до 65 мм, длину от 60 м до 70 м, ширину от 3 м до 9 м, с общим количеством от 20 до 50 сетей (в каждой комбинации) из шелка и искусственных волокон. В результате 15 разового забрасывания и сбора сетей от 0,5 км до 5 км от берега на глубину от 1 м до 12 м, были подсчитаны 155 образцов судака обыкновенного (*Sander lucioperca*), длиной от 25 см до 65 см, весом от 400 гр до 5000 гр; 16 образцов серебряного карася (*Carassius gibelio*) длиной от 22 см до 25 см, весом от 300 г до 350 г; 360 образцов аральской плотвы (*Rutilus aralensis*) длиной от 12 см до 23 см, весом от 200 гр до 300 гр; 24 образца карпа обыкновенного (*Cyprinus carpio*) длиной от 25 см до 55 см, весом от 350 гр до 5000 гр и 1 образец Аральской шемей (*Chalcarburnus chalcaoides aralensis*) длиной 25 см, весом 300 гр (таблица 2).

Ячейки для рыболовных сетей системы озер Айдар-Арнасой на озере Айдар имели размер от 28 мм до 60 мм, длину от 60 м до 70 м, ширину от 3 м до 10 м, с общим количеством от 10 до 40 сетей (в каждой комбинации) из шелка и искусственных волокон. В результате 17 разового забрасывания и сбора сетей от 0,1 км до 5 км от берега на глубину от 2 м до 15 м, были подсчитаны 100 образцов судака обыкновенного (*Sander lucioperca*), длиной от 25 см до 45 см, весом от 400 гр до 1900 гр; 10 образцов серебряного карася (*Carassius gibelio*) длиной от 18 см до 28 см, весом от 220 гр до 450 гр; 255 образцов аральской плотвы (*Rutilus aralensis*) длиной от 18 см до 24 см, весом от 200 гр до 300 гр; 14 образцов карпа обыкновенного (*Cyprinus carpio*) длиной от 20 см до 40 см, весом от 250 гр до 950 гр (таблица 3).

Результаты подсчета двух комплексных контрольных отловов на озере Тузкан озерной системы Айдар-Арнасай, проведенных в летнем и осеннем сезонах

№	Виды выловленных рыб	Показатели размера выловленных образцов рыб				Положение опускания рыболовной сети				Показатели рыболовных сетей			
		Длина (см)	Вес (гр)	Количество (штук)	Общий вес (кг)	Удаленность от берега (км)	Текущая глубина озера (м)	Длина (м)	Ширина (м)	Размеры садков (мм)	Кол. (штук)		
1	Судак обыкновенный (<i>Sander lucionegca</i> , (Linnaeus, 1758))	18-35	100-500	2	0,6	0,1	3-5	60-65	3-5	30-32	25		
		30-35	350-400	55	19	4-5	10-15	60-70	3-4	32	20		
		38-48	1,5-2	6	5-6	1,5-2	7-8	70	9-10	55-60	30		
		25-40	350	47	16,5	1-1,5	3-4	60-70	3-4	32	40		
		38-40	500	10	5,5-6	1,5-2	6-7	70	10	45	50		
2	Серебряный карась (<i>Carassius gibelio</i> , (Bloch, 1782))	16	200	1	0,2	0,05-0,1	2-5	60-65	3-5	30-32	40		
		29-30	400-500	4	1,8	1,5-2	7-8	60-70	9-10	30-32	25		
		20-25	400	6	2-2,4	1-1,5	3-4	60-70	3-4	32	20		
		29,5-32	440	2	0,9	1,5-2	6-7	70	10	45	25		
		18-25	200-300	74	18,5	0,5-0,1	2-5	60-65	3-5	30-32	40		
3	Аральская плотва (<i>Rutilus aralensis</i> , (Berg, 1916))	17-23	200-250	120	27,6	1-1,5	5-5,5	60-70	9-10	28-30-32	20		
		17-24	250	20	5-5,5	1-1,5	3-4	60-70	3-4	32-36	25		
		18	200	1	0,2	0,05-0,1	2-5	60-65	3-5	30-32	35		
4	Карп обыкновенный (<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> , (Linnaeus, 1759))	22-25	500	2	0,5	4-5	10-15	60-70	3-4	32	40		
		45	900	1	0,9	1,5-2	6-7	70	10	45	25		
5	Жерех аральский (<i>Aspius aspius ibloides</i> , (Kessler, 1872))	20	220	1	0,22	0,05-0,1	2-5	60-65	3-5	30-32	40		

Примечание: В таблице приведены результаты, полученные по 16 участкам (контурам) озера Тузкан. В данном случае во избежении неудобства или недоразумений, общие показатели единиц измерения не представлены.

Таблица 1

Таблица 2
 Результаты подсчета двух комплексных контрольных отловов на озере Восточный Арнасай озерной системы Айдар-Арнасай, проведённых в летнем и осеннем сезонах

№	Виды выловленных рыб	Показатели размера выловленных образцов рыб						Положение опускания рыболовной сети					Показатели рыболовных сетей			
		Длина (см)	Вес (гр)	Количество (штук)	Общий вес (кг)	Удалённость от берега (км)	Текущая глубина озера (м)	Длина (м)	Ширина (м)	Размеры садков (мм)	Кол. (штук)					
1	Судак обыкновенный (<i>Sander lucioperca</i> , (Linnaeus, 1758))	45-50	1600-2000	30	55-60	4-5	8-10	60-70	3-4	50	35					
		30-40	700-800	22	18-19	3-4	6-8	70	3-4	55	50					
		55-65	3000-5000	15	55-60	1-2	10-12	60-70	8-9	65	60					
		25-30	400	5	2-2,5	0,5-0,8	3-4	60-70	3-4	32	25					
		25-50	600	83	49,8	1,5-2	6-8	60-70	3-4	40-36-32	25					
2	Серебряный карась (<i>Carassius gibelio</i> , (Bloch, 1782))	22-25	300	16	5-5,5	1,5-2	6-8	60-70	3-4	40-36-32	35					
		12-20	250	85	25	4-5	7-8	60-70	3-4	30	10					
3	Аральская плотва (<i>Rutilus aralensis</i> , (Berg, 1916))	18-20	300	15	3-5	1-2	8-9	60-70	3-4	40	25					
		17-23	220	100	22	0,8	1-1,5	60-70	3-4	32	15					
		18-22	200-250	100	25	2	6-7	60-70	3-4	28	20					
		18-23	200-250	60	13,8	1,5-2	6-8	60-70	3-4	32	30					
4	Карп обыкновенный (<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> , (Linnaeus, 1759))	30-35	750	4	3	4-5	9-10	60-70	3-4	32	25					
		50-55	3000-5000	12	48-50	2	10-12	60-70	8-9	65	15					
		25-30	350	8	2,5	1,5-2	6-8	60-70	3-4	40-36-35	30					
5	Аральская шемая (<i>Chalcarburtus chalcaoides</i> <i>aralensis</i> (Berg, 1923))	25	300	1	0,3	4-5	9-10	60-70	3-4	32	20					

Примечание: В таблице приведены результаты, полученные по 15 участкам (контурам) озера Восточный Туркестан. В данном случае во избежении неудобства или недоразумений, общие показатели единиц измерения не предоставлены.

Таблица 3

Результаты подсчета двух комплексных контрольных отловов на озере Айдар озерной системы Айдар-Арнасай, проведённых в летнем и осеннем сезонах

№	Виды выловленных рыб	Показатели размера выловленных образцов				Положение опускания рыболовной сети				Показатели рыболовных сетей			
		Длина (см)	Вес (гр)	Количество (штук)	Общий вес (кг)	Удалённость от берега (км)	Текущая глубина озера (м)	Длина (м)	Ширина (м)	Размеры садков (мм)	Кол. (штук)		
1	Судак обыкновенный (<i>Sander lucioperca</i> , (Linnaeus, 1758))	25-35	400-500	2	0,9	1	6-8	60-65	3-5	30-32	25		
		30-35	500-700	50	30	4-5	10-15	60-70	3-4	32	20		
		30-35	600-700	2	1,3-1,4	1-1,5	2-3	60-70	7-8	40	10		
		35-45	1,5-1,9	6	9-10	1,5-2	7-8	70	9-10	55-60	35		
		25-30	450	40	18,5	1-1,5	4-5	60-70	3-4	32	30		
2	Серебристый карась (<i>Carassius gibelio</i> , (Bloch, 1782))	18	220	1	0,22	1	5-6	60-65	3-5	30-32	25		
		18-20	200-240	5	1,5-1,8	1-1,5	2-4	60-70	7-8	40	30		
		25-28	400-450	4	1,8	4-5	9-10	60-70	9-10	30-32	20		
		18-23	250-300	54	14,5	0,5-0,1	2-5	60-65	3-5	30-32	40		
		18	200	1	0,2	1-1,5	2-4	60-70	7-8	40	15		
3	Аральская плотва (<i>Rutilus aralensis</i> , (Berg, 1916))	18-20	200-250	70	16	2-2,5	6-7	60-70	6-7	28-33	50		
		18-23	200-250	100	25,6	1-1,5	5-5,5	60-70	9-10	28-30-32	20		
		19-24	230	30	5-6	1-1,5	3-4	60-70	3-4	32-36	25		
		20	250	2	0,5	1-1,5	4-5	60-65	3-5	30-32	35		
		25-28	700	4	2,4	4-5	10-15	60-70	3-4	32	40		
4	Карп обыкновенный (<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> , (Linnaeus, 1759))	20-22	300-400	5	2-2,5	1-1,5	2-4	60-70	7-8	40	10		
		40	950	3	2,8	2-3	6-7	70	10	50	20		

Примечание: В таблице приведены результаты, полученные по 17 участкам (контурам) озера Айдар. В данном случае во избежении неудобства или недоразумений, общие показатели единицы измерения не представлены

Обсуждение полученных результатов. В системе озер Айдар-Арнасой, как указано в показателях рыболовства за период с 1990 по 1999 год, можно видеть, что вместе с судаком обыкновенным, серебряным карасём, аральской плотвой и карпом обыкновенным в равных количествах встречались Восточный лещ, белый толстолобик, Аральский красногубый жерех, сом, Амурский змеёголов и щука, а также в отдельные годы в очень малых количествах встречались такие виды рыб, как чехонь и Самаркандская храмуля (Хуршут, 2001). В ходе проведенных нами контрольных отловов по численности и показателям встречаемости такие виды, как судак обыкновенный, серебристый карась, аральская плотва и карп обыкновенный в основном занимали ведущие позиции. А такие виды как щука, чехонь и Самаркандская храмуля не встречались.

Выводы. В общей сложности в количестве 48 раз был проведён процесс заброса и поднятия рыболовной сети. Количество комбинаций (сумм) каждой заброски сети составляло в среднем 25 раз. При этом в сетях, которые были заброшены далеко от берега и глубоких частях озера, в основном встречались белые судаки и карпы. Образцы серебряного карася встречались в относительно небольшом количестве. Недалеко от побережья и на глубине 3-4 м по численности в основном доминировала аральская плотва. Обнаружено, что

количество видов рыб, имеющих промысловое значение в озере Восточный Арнасой озёрной системы Айдар-Арнасой, выше по сравнению с озерами Тузкан и Айдар. Встречаемая в озере Восточный Арнасай аральская шемая в других частях системы озёр не наблюдалась. Причиной этого может являться чистота пресной воды в данном озере. В разрезе по видам рыб имеющих промысловое значение, во всех частях системы озер Айдар-Арнасой наблюдалось распространение большого количества аральской плотвы. Обнаружено, что серебристый карась встречается в меньшем количестве по сравнению с другими видами рыб. В ходе проведенных контролируемых отловов выявлено, что образцы рыб имели большой коэффициент попадания в сети из искусственного волокна, чем в сети из шелкового волокна.

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METABOLISM OF NEUROMEDIATORY AMINO ACIDS IN DIFFERENT BRAIN DIVISIONS**Omar Parvin Mirdamat***Sumgayit State University, Sumgayit, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

The morpho-functional differentiation and maturation of different departments of the brain are accompanied by changes in the amount of number of biologically active substances, amino acids, proteins, and lipids. When studying the protein metabolism occurring in nerve tissue, it was determined that this tissue contains many substituted and non-substituted amino acids and enzymes involved in amino acid metabolism. These indicate that amino acid metabolism and protein biosynthesis occur with particular intensity in nervous tissue.

Keywords: amino acid, lipid, postnatal, cytomorphological, electrophysiological, GABA-gamma aminobutyric acid

Introduction

Studying the activity of the central nervous system is one of the most demanding and particularly important issues facing the science of neurophysiology. The central nervous system creates interaction between the cells, tissues and individual parts of the body, ensuring their completeness. It also regulates the processes in the body and keeps all its activities under control by directing the work of the organs. It depends on the functional state of the CNS in the relationship between the organism and the external environment [1].

Among the functional structures of the central nervous system, the cerebral cortex is the body's cardiovascular system, respiratory system, muscle tone, and metabolism, etc. combines complex biological functions related to Cerebral cortex departments, as well as the coordination of movement, homeostasis protection, integrate the primary learning centres [4,7].

According to literature sources, shell derivatives and morpho-functional differentiation of the brain begin to form in the early stage of postnatal ontogenesis. In early postnatal ontogenesis, fundamental cytomorphological and electrophysiological changes take place in different departments of the brain [1,2].

It has been established that the functional maturation of separate structures of the brain and subcortical derivatives begins at different times.

As it was discovered, the functional maturity of brain structures of humans and different species of animals does not proceed with the same intensity in postnatal ontogeny.

In early postnatal ontogeny, the electrical activity of the brain of animals does not differ significantly for sleep and wakefulness. This is explained by the fact that the maturation of the functional maturity and structural organization of different departments of the brain corresponds to the state of the reticular system, ascending departments of the thalamus nucleus.

The variation in the speed of emergence of action forms of conditioned reflex reactions and the localization of action forms corresponds to the later stages of postnatal ontogenesis. Therefore, compared to general motor acts, the performance of local responses is one of the most complex issues of postnatal ontogenesis for the animal's central nervous system [3,4].

It is known from literary sources that the level of functional development in the cerebral cortex and subcortical structure is determined in the process of ontogenesis. It is observed in the morphological improvements in the brain. The maturation of the central nervous system in corresponding stages and the determination of its electrical activity stabilizes at the end of the first month of life in animals belonging to relatively low levels of phylogenetic development. Functional formation in the cortical structures of the brain of hares ends in the 3rd and 4th months.

The development of the brain refers to the period from the neonatal stage to the period of sexual maturity [5,7]. According to the morphological, electrophysiological, biochemical and compositional indicators obtained by reflective methods, the functional and morphological maturity of the brain in postnatal ontogeny can be classified as follows.

The first stage covers the first two stages of life. At this time, the mass of the brain increases intensively. The second stage covers the period up to the 45th day of life, and at this time, although the intensity of the increase in the mass of the brain decreases, the process stops completely. In the third stage, the growth of its mass up to three months of age is practically stopped.

In mammals, CNS indicators are characterized by the development of the neocortex. Its cytoarchitectonics (associative, projection zones, etc.) are used in the process of development of the cerebral cortex in phylogeny and ontogeny in increasing the differentiation of neuron organizations: in the formation of neurons of different shapes, in the increase of their quantity, in the change of synaptic contact types, in the development of protrusions, etc.

Neurons in the cerebral cortex differ according to their distribution opposition, their shape and structure, and their size, as well as the functional relevance of biochemical processes.

The morphological characteristics of pyramidal neurons include their large size, multi-branching of dendrites, an abundance of communication with other cells, large mass and distance of the axon from the body of the neuron.

On the 10th-12th days of postnatal ontogenesis, the amount of mature pyramidal neurons increases, the volume of the cytoplasm increases, and the growth of

basal dendrites is strong in its apical part. At this time, a new qualitative form of synaptic contact is created.

In newborns, the conditioned reflex is weak. This is due to the diversity of maturation of the brain and different departments of the cerebral cortex.

The development of excitation and inhibition of the main processes in the cerebral cortex determines the provision of conditioned reflex activity. The highest level of cortical processes is manifested in island rabbits at 35-45 days.

As a result of a series of neuro-histological studies, neurons were classified according to their shape, size, and degree of branching of axons and dendrites. Morpho-functional correction of neurons and the diversity of internal structures of synaptic neurons were revealed through the electron microscope.

Recently, special attention has been paid to the study of the sensitivity of immature neurons to mediators and their functional nature in different periods of postnatal ontogenesis. As a result of studying the electrophysiological indicators of neurons in the embryo and early postnatal ontogenesis, it was revealed that there is an interaction between the structure of the developing neuron and its function. Quality was observed on the basis of morphological changes according to electrophysiological phenomenon indicators.

It was determined by the conducted research that the morpho-functional differentiation and maturation of various departments of the brain are accompanied by changes in the amount of a number of biologically active substances, amino acids, proteins, and lipids. This idea was confirmed by a number of parallel biochemical studies [4,5,6].

There is a high pool of proteins and amino acids in the brain. Amino acids and proteins occupy a central position in nitrogen metabolism.

When studying the protein metabolism occurring in nerve tissue, it was determined that this tissue contains many substituted and non-substituted amino acids and enzymes involved in amino acid metabolism. These indicate that amino acid metabolism and protein biosynthesis occur with extraordinary intensity in nervous tissue.

Glutamic acid has a special role in the metabolism of the brain. Ammonia generated in nerve tissue is mainly neutralized by combining with glutamic acid. Glutamic acid combines with ammonia and turns into glutamine, which is harmless to nerve tissue. So, while glutamine easily passes from the blood to the cerebrospinal fluid, glutamic acid can cross the blood-brain barrier with great difficulty. It is hypothesized that glutamic acid is aminated to pass from the blood to the nerve tissue. must be converted to glutamine. Glutamic acid can also be produced synthetically in nervous tissue. Part of the ammonia produced in the brain is used for the synthesis of glutamic acid. QABA, which is an exchange product of glutamic acid, occupies an important place in the metabolism of neurons. Glutamic acid in nerve tissue is sharply separated from other

amino acids due to its quantity and participation in metabolic processes. Among its exchange products, glutamine, metaglutarate, and gamma-amino fatty acid occupy a critical place in the metabolism of neurons. In nerve tissue, glutamic acid is sharply separated from other amino acids by its quantity and participation in metabolic processes. Of its exchange products, glutamine, metaglutarate and gamma-amino fatty acid are particularly active substances. Together, they make up more than half of the brain's amino acid pool. The metabolism of glutamic acid consists of a series of complex reactions catalyzed by specific enzymes. The glutamate dehydrogenase enzyme, which is specific for brain tissue, is involved in the synthesis of glutamic acid but is also very sensitive to the increase of ammonia in the brain. When excess ammonia accumulates in the brain, the glutamate dehydrogenase enzyme uses most of it in the conversion reaction of glutamic acid. Glutaminetase enzyme is also involved in this process.

It is known that gamma-amino-fatty acid plays an important role in the exchange processes in the brain tissue. Although glutamine is not oxidized in the brain tissue, it is less useful for the energy supply of the brain and acts as a donor of amino groups for the synthesis of substituted amino acids. RETURN is particularly characteristic of the brain. It is formed as a result of the separation of a carboxyl group from glutamic acid.

The determination of the physiological role of QABA as an inhibitory mediator, its participation in bioenergetic processes, and the significance of the intracellular position in the permeability of the cell membrane in complex metabolic processes are significant for the cytochemical studies carried out consistently.

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ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MODERN ASPECTS OF GUARANTEEING THE STABILITY OF CONTRACTS IN INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS

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Abstract

In modern conditions, compared to the earlier periods, the attitude of the parties to the contract during the preparation of contracts in international business has changed significantly. An international business contract is the main driver of agreement between the business participants. It significantly determines the successful state of business. The purpose of the contract is to harmonize international business relations. Along with the development of blockchain technology and digital communication systems at the modern stage, the interest in smart contract as the most effective tool of this technology is growing. It is through the smart contract that the business can receive the benefits resulted from the development of information technology.

Keywords: Business contracts, legal systems, human factor, blockchain system, smart contract

The main text

Among the many factors affecting international business, one of the important and "influential" factors is the main legislative and legal acts, laws of both own and host countries. Every step from the company's initial activity to the international market is regulated and the main goal is reached based on them. This factor is equally crucial for all countries - whether it is a producer or a consumer.

In general, the legal systems of countries differ due to their cultural, historical or political background. There are three types of legal systems: general, civil and religious. It is these three main signs that create a mechanism for regulating international relations all over the world, including in the field of international business.

General law is based on the collective experience of making decisions accumulated throughout the history of the country on separate judicial activities. Laws governing the conduct of business are characterized by their specificity, which creates a problem for misinformed entrepreneurs. Religious law is based on officially established rules of faith and religion. Theocracy is a management form that regulates civil and criminal behavior of citizens. It happens that sometimes religious law can cause significant problems in the company's activities.

For example: according to the Muslim Koran, charging interest on a loan is considered an unfair exploitation of the poor. Therefore, financial organizations are forced to develop and implement alternative options. Systems based on religious law are also characterized by other features. For example, lack of appropriate court procedures and appeal filing procedures, etc. All this depends on the religious traditions of the country.

In modern conditions, compared to the earlier periods, the attitude of the parties to the contract during the preparation of contracts in international business

has changed significantly. In particular, paying attention to and accounting for such details became equally important, which were previously, on the contrary, neglected. In this way, contractors emphasize mutual respect for partners, which may be related to the traditions, religion, and national values of the partner country. Taking into account the partner's interests and making certain concessions when making decisions is accepted in international business. Obviously, this does not mean putting one's own interests in the background and withdrawing one's positions as a result of concessions. We are talking about newly formed and established signs of mutual respect and collegiality. In such a case, both sides of the contract remain winners. A reliable and solid relationship is formed. Obviously, both parties to the contract should equally try and aim to acquire a reliable and long-term partner, who in return is ready to take into account the same reverse actions.

At the same time, we cannot ignore the fact that there are a number of issues and strictly controlled regulations, which must be observed and fulfilled, and no changes can be made there by the parties. In particular, international law plays an important role in international business, it regulates relations between states. By law, one country can force another to agree to unacceptable policy changes, using trade restrictions and sanctions. Sanctions can be: quota, refusal of new credits, restriction of access to high-tech products, boycott of the country's goods, etc. An international business contract is a document necessary to achieve business goals, which protects intellectual property, trade secrets and reduces risk in the international market. It can be said that an international business contract is the main driver of agreement between business participants. It significantly determines the successful state of business. The purpose of the contract is to harmonize international business relations.

In order to avoid business failure, it is necessary that all terms of the contract to be properly observed and drafted by lawyers. Depending on the international

nature of the contract, it may be defined in different ways. International business contracts represent an important connection between two or more states and impose certain obligations on all parties to each other. The issues of concluding and canceling the contract, as well as its validity, are legally regulated by international law, the positions of the parties are clearly reflected in it.

The role of statistical data in contracts and international business is important. In general, statistics and statistical data help consumers, governments, investors and other business stakeholders to make better decisions and develop the future. Consumers need statistics to know when and where to buy the goods or services they need and want. On the other hand, businesses actively use statistical information to make full-fledged decisions: what, where, how much to produce. Statistical information allows for forecasting future periods, how much production can be expanded or vice versa, orders the time of market reduction and displacement, etc.

The government of any country makes important decisions and changes based on statistical information, along with business. From which areas to receive stable and guaranteed payments, how and in what way to attract new and additional resources, as well as where, in what amount and priority to spend the existing revenues, etc.

The modern statistical system, with its full-fledged and universally understandable information, provides considerable assistance to international business partners in business proposals and offers, in the preparation of international contracts, in obtaining any necessary information about each other. It is for this purpose that the national accounts system, monetary and financial statistics, balance of payments statistics and international investment situation, government finance statistics were developed by the specialists of the statistical service of international organizations. However, at every stage of human development, new economic challenges arise that require statistical study and analysis. Along with the mentioned indicators, a number of international regulatory legal acts, contracts play an important role in the signing of international business contracts: The Charter of the United Nations, the Convention on Climate Change, the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants.

International contract is the main source of international law. The importance of international law is great in international business. Therefore, the role of the contract is also clear. The purpose of an international business contract is to regulate important issues between states or organizations.

Due to the fact that the contract is signed between the parties, in the process of doing business, arise important issues, the parties' positions, requirements, goals, which must be protected and inviolable in the future.

Contract is a very important factor in the regulation of international business. Due to the fact that business is associated with constant risk, many changes and even disagreements between parties, it is necessary to

have a document that will legally guarantee the satisfaction of all the requirements, conditions, positions, and wishes of business producers.

If a business with an international level does not have a contract between the parties, the possibility of its failure will increase and the level of risks will increase. Also, when the company is in the international market and has a similar type of responsibility, it is necessary to verify each of its actions in the form of a contract to avoid unpleasant consequences in the future. A contract is a guarantee that every obligation that exists between the parties is reliable. Nowadays, contractual business relationships, both domestically and internationally, have grown considerably. Due to the fact that everything in the world is constantly changing, people are constantly looking for stability or "subject" that will guarantee stability. It is the contract that guarantees stability in the regulation of international business

Thus, a stable and successful international business regulation is impossible without a contract, the legal norms that it possesses make it unique in this respect, because only a contract can fulfill the regulation of business legally in the long term and its future in a risky world.

Today, quite a lot is changing in terms of international contracts and the conclusion of contracts in general, and most importantly, increasing the stability and reliability of contracts. We would like to express our modest opinion regarding the current news

With the development of blockchain technologies and digital communication systems at the modern stage, the interest in smart contract as the most effective tool of the said technology is growing. It is through the smart contract that the business can receive the benefits that result from the development of information technology.

Talking about smart contract became relevant after the appearance of blockchain and cryptocurrency in the Internet space. Blockchain and smart contract are considered as a legally recognized method of data storage, provided that they do will not contradict with existing rules and laws. An electronic signature carried out in the blockchain system is interpreted as having legal force. If the parties have chosen the blockchain as their data storage location, then the data from such a source is considered legally valid. A contract cannot be deprived of legal force or enforcement on the grounds that an electronic signature was used when concluding the contract and the terms are given in the form of a smart contract.

Electronic signature in the blockchain system is recognized by law. A signature and contract protected by blockchain technology is considered electronic.

At the level of international business, harmonization and standardization of common standards, norms and characteristics around smart contracts are underway under the auspices of blockchain technology. An international technical committee - ISO/TC307: «Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies» has been created under the leadership of the International Organization for Standardization, which works on specific standards, in specific registries, including smart contracts. The committee is faced with the task of

whether a smart contract will be able to simplify or replace legal mechanisms.

The success of the smart contract and the efficiency of business relationship regulation mostly depend on the synchronous development of technical and legal progress. Along with the development of digital technologies, legislative support will significantly increase the scale of smart contracts, allowing them to be widely used in today's rather "accelerated" world pulse. Today, smart contracts can be used in both commercial and financial transactions, as well as social transactions: inheritance, labor and insurance relations. In Georgia, since 2017, the law "On Electronic Documents and Electronic Trust Services" is in force. It is desirable to adopt such a legislative act as the law "On Digital Economy". This would enable the deployment and operation of smart contracts. Transactions in a number of business areas or legal matters of various legal significance and types would automatically be regulated.

Today, a very common and widely known type of smart contract is blockchain. It is a database that is automatically managed, it does not have a single center. Information is stored and updated simultaneously, in different devices. Blockchain securely stores information, at the same time, also providing key information to the smart contract. Blockchain increases reliability in the sense that there is a greater trust factor between the parties due to the existence of a uniform document. Several persons are guaranteed with unchanged information and most importantly, technical attack is excluded.

There are two types of existing blockchain platforms: public and private (blockchain consortia). Their use depends on the type of projects. In particular, blockchain is used where it is necessary to eliminate the distrust factor (there is distrust between partners...), or it is impossible to use a centralized platform.

Smart contracts were soon "accepted" and approved, because they are characterized by the main features that characterize today's world relations, first of all, quickness and less time spending. Second and important - the main value of the contract is to make the obligation self-fulfilling, it no longer depends on or minimizes the risks, relieves the participants of the contract and leaves them with the least chance of not fulfilling their obligations. To hide important facts and to violate the deadlines. Because the rights of the parties are so strictly limited, the risks are less. As a result, the

business receives stable income, better management of receivables and payables, there are fewer commercial and financial disputes.

In fact, a smart contract is similar to a physical contract, the difference is that it is digital, is a computer program, and is stored in the blockchain system. It is called the smart contract software model. It establishes the rules of business transactions, negotiations, automatically confirms the terms of performance and enforcement.

So, smart contracts are considered as a guarantee of the stability of contracts in international business. The competitive environment of the modern market economy does not allow for the luxury of time. The Covid-19 pandemic also clearly showed us that negotiation and agreement can be done without meetings and direct connections, and moreover, it is associated with lower costs. It is important technologies to be modern and in good order.

The factor of human and human relations gradually moves to the background. We are getting used to the standards and framework of business relationships that will only be offered by the programs. Over time, the features that differentiate countries and states, which we talked about at the beginning of the article, will no longer be remembered. No one will have the obligation to take into account the interests of the partner... We will all be organized and adjusted to the same standards in the same digital world.

And will this be a modern guarantor of the stability of contracts in international business!?

In an automatically managed database created by a person, where information is stored and updated simultaneously, in different devices, blockchain increases reliability in the sense that there is a greater trust factor between the parties due to the existence of a uniform document and it can be confidently claimed that this is a guarantee of reliability?!

The current situation is a time factor. Human relations are indispensable even at the peak of technological progress. Blockchain trustworthiness and smart contracts will only partially replace human relationships.

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MEDICAL SCIENCES

PHOTODYNAMIC THERAPY, TSKALTUBO (GEORGIA) WATER RADON HORMESIS AND ORAL MICROBIOLOGY

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Abstract

Combined effect of “Rada Dent” and Tskhaltubo water (inhalation of Tskhaltubo water and using it as a mouthwash) slowly reduces and cures inflammation caused by periodontitis and gingivitis, which can be explained by the unique characteristics of “Rada Dent” and Tskaltubo water. At the present moment, information on the characteristics of only a few thousand microorganisms making up normal microflora of the oral cavity is available. These are bacteria, viruses, fungi and protozoa.

The majority of Gram-positive Cocci in the oral cavity is represented by heterogeneous group of Streptococci, which are active participants in damaging hard tooth and periodontal tissues.

“Rada Dent” and Tskaltubo water hormesis proved successful in slowing down and curing oral inflammation.

Keywords: Photodynamic therapy, radonized water, periodontitis, gingivitis, microflora.

Introductoin

Tskaltubo mineral water, located in Georgia (<https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CAMQw7AJahcKEwjww9LXzdj4AhUAAAAAHQAAA AAAg&url=https%3A%2F%2Ftskaltuboresort.ge%2Feng&psig=AOv-Vaw2bzLOv3T5lV5ch4lQA4pvn&ust=1656796325261966>) is distinguished by the fact that each ingredient is below the lower threshold of the norm.

Chemical composition of Tskaltubo springs is stable and unchanged in time. Juxtaposition of chemical analyses conducted throughout the recent 70-80 year corroborates the mentioned.

Tskaltubo mineral water is distinguished by solid physical and chemical characteristics. It contains noble gas – Radon, large amount of Nitrogen and Helium. It belongs to the category of waters containing small amount of Radon (1-2,7 nCi/L; or 3-7,5 unit; or 40-100 Bq), Chlorine-Hydrocarbonate-Sulfate, Sodium-Magnesium-Calcium – total mineralization 0,7-0,8 g/L. 24-hour yield for the springs amounts to 13-15 million liters. Highly effective medicinal and preventive effect of the spring waters is due to complex composition and peculiar combination of principle components composed of sodium. The natural temperature (+33-35°C) allows to use it without warming up.

Biologically active microelements (Iodine, Bromine, Manganese, Lithium, Bohrium, Zinc, Strontium, and Copper) have been discovered in the Tskaltubo mineral waters, which play an important role in the vitality of the body.

20-25% of the world’s adult population suffer from periodontal diseases, most widespread of which are periodontitis and gingivitis.

At the moment, information on the characteristics of only a few thousand microorganisms that make up normal microflora of the oral cavity is available. Among them are bacteria, viruses, fungi and protozoa. Amid the microbes of the oral cavity, autochthonous and allochthonous variety are more prominent. Allochthonous-immigrants are microflora from other biotopes (nose and throat, intestines and etc.) of the host and environment. From autochthonous microflora, obligate, which always live in the oral cavity and temporary-transitory, which is frequently made up of pathogenic or conditionally pathogenic bacteria.

The majority of gram-positive oral Cocci are heterogeneous group of Streptococci of low virulence, which are active participants of processes that lead to damaging periodontal tissue [1]. These are Streptococcus mutans, S.mitis, S. Salivarius. The second group of gram-positive Cocci are Peptococci. Peptococci are most frequently associated with Fusobacteria and spirochetes during caries, pulpitis, periodontitis, and dental abscess.

Gram-negative anaerobic Cocci in the oral cavity are Veillonella and gram-positive bacillus are Lactobacillus; Gram-negative anaerobic and microaerophilic bacteria most frequently belong to Bacteroides group; and yeasts named Candida produce vitamins essential for Lactobacteria to grow. The latter produce lactic acid during metabolism that causes increasing acidity of the environment, hinders adhesion and yeast colonization, which in turn leads to reduction in the number of vitamins essential to restrict growth in some microorganisms.

The oxygen level is significantly lowered in the periodontal and pseudo-pockets, mucous folds. This creates advantageous conditions for development of

such anaerobes as Fusobacteria, Bacteriodes, Leptotrichia, Spirochaete [2]. 100 million anaerobic microorganism could be in 1 ml of saliva [3]. The nature of food has a big influence on the qualitative and quantitative index of oral microflora: increased amount of sucrose leads to increased share of Streptococci and Lactobacteria, however glucose does not have such influence. While these processes are ongoing, toxic genes gain control over ADP-ribosyltransferase enzyme activity, which produces a cascade of reactions and breaks down cyclic adenosine monophosphate acid (AMP) synthesis, therefore, breaking down cyclic synthesis in the given cell.[4]

The toxicity of endotoxins is noticed during high concentration levels. They can activate complimentary systems, for example, blood coagulation, they impact enzyme systems of the body, etc. Platelet membrane, macrophages, lymphocytes and capillary endothelium have binding receptors. Endotoxin activity is based upon their concentration. In low doses, they can activate phagocytosis and other protective reactions [5.6]. Pathogenic enzymes synthesize reactions, which are directed at producing toxic products or disrupt cell and tissue. Fibrinolysis and hyaluronidase facilitate toxin spread, due to which microbes easily penetrate the tissue and cause its disruption, and phospholipase causes necrosis. As for Staphylococci and Streptococci, hemolysins lyse erythrocytes and leucocytes [7.8].

Plasma coagulase of Staphylococci and other microorganisms – peptidase activates blood coagulation through catalyzing prothrombin into thrombin and creates fibrin layer around microbial cells. We studied microbial characteristics in the oral fluid during periodontitis [9]. Strains of microflora were identified in each

patient before starting a treatment. The most frequently studied strains by us are as follows: Streptococcus intermedius, Prevotella spp., Fusobacterium spp.

Principal objective for us is to study a method for photodynamic therapy, its effect on inflammatory diseases of the oral cavity. Photodynamic therapy has been broadly used during the last decade [2]. This method of treatment was popular both in treating oncological and non-oncological, inflammatory diseases (such as gingivitis and periodontitis) in the fields of stomatology and medicine.

Material and methods.

We observed compound effect of photosensitizer “Rada Dent”, machine “Photodin-K” and inhalation of Radon in Tskhaltubo water and using it as a mouthwash. At the beginning, once every 6 months and later after 1 or 2 years. Combination therapy includes scaling and root instrumentation, photodynamic therapy [10] and Radon inhalation. The combination therapy allows us to treat mild forms of gingivitis and periodontitis in patients without antibiotics or other medications.

The main reasons the patients present to us are bleeding gums, unpleasant smell, and insufficient hygiene. The insufficient hygiene is the principal reason for forming a bacterial biofilm.

The patients were healthy and systemic diseases were not recorded, which has a huge impact on the oral mucosa.

Stabilized, resistant microflora is mainly represented with microaerophilic Streptococci in the oral fluid: Streptococcus sanguis, Streptococcus salivarius, Streptococcus mitis, also Enterobacter spp. and Lactobacillus spp.

Table 1

Microflora	Before treatment		After treatment	
	N	%	N	%
<i>St. intermedius</i>	9	60	8	46,4
<i>St. haemolyticus</i>	1	6,8	0	0
<i>Str. Sanguis</i>	10	72,9	0	0
<i>Str. Mitis</i>	10	72,0	7	42
<i>Str. Faecium</i>	0	0	0	0
<i>Str. Salivarius</i>	13	81	11	67,2
<i>Str. Viridians</i>	6	34,1	5	27,6
<i>C. albicans</i>	0	0	4	27,2
<i>Lactobacillus spp.</i>	2	13,3	2	13,3
<i>Prevotella spp.</i>	12	81	5	25,5
<i>Enterobacter spp.</i>	1	6,6	1	6,6
<i>Fusobacterium spp.</i>	4	27,1	2	14,1

n – Number of patients (n=15) in the group

Microbial characteristics: after treating mild and average forms of periodontitis with photodynamic therapy and Tskaltubo water hormesis, frequency of potential periodontopathic pathogen (Prevotella spp., Bacteriodes spp., Streptococcus intermedius) production was observed to reduce alongside with stabilized resistant oral microflora (Streptococcus sanguis, Streptococcus salivarius, Streptococcus salivarius, St.) and increase in the frequency of candida albicans production was recorded (Table 1).

Quantitative assessment of microorganisms and change in the numbers gives us a more objective data. For statistical convenience, CFU/ml was recalculated with a common logarithm. After treatment, significant reduction of microorganisms was observed compared to the data obtained before treatment ($p < 0.05$) and some variety totally disappeared.

(Table 2)

Microbial characteristics: treating patients with mild and average forms of periodontitis with photodynamic therapy [11] and Tskaltubo water hormesis (lgCFU/ml, $M \pm \delta$)

Table 2

Microorganisms	Before treatment	After treatment
<i>St. aureus</i>	5,7	3
<i>Str. Intermedius</i>	7,4±0,4	2,3±0,4
<i>Str. Haemolyticus</i>	4,7	–
<i>Str. Sangvis</i>	5,6±0,3	–
<i>Str. Mitis</i>	7,7±0,1	1,9±0,3
<i>Str. Salivarius</i>	6,8±0,4	2,4±0,3
<i>C. albicans</i>	–	3,6±0,1

After the treatment, the majority of Streptococci characteristic to normal flora - *Streptococcus sanguis*, *Streptococcus salivarius*, *Streptococcus mitis* – reduced significantly from lg 7.7 ± 0.1 to lg 1.9 ± 0.3, and the representatives of *Streptococcus* almost totally disappeared. The number of *Streptococcus intermedius*, *Stafilococcus aureus* significantly reduced and *Streptococcus haemolyticus* totally disappeared. However, the number of *Candida* increased to lg 3.6 ± 0.1.

Results and discussion:

To illustrate clinical course of gingivitis, we are providing an excerpt from a patient's outpatient card, who was under our observation. A patient D. M. presented in the Department of Stomatology complaining of unpleasant smell, bleeding gum during brushing the teeth, sometimes during biting solid food, gum swelling and hyperemia.

According to the patient, gum bleeding started approximately 3 months ago. They did not visit a doctor, did not undergo any kind of treatment.

During oral examination, oral mucosa is pale pink, shiny, damp. Gingival margin on the upper and lower jaw is hyperemic, interdental papilla are swollen, bleeding was observed during probing, false pockets, difficulty of brushing the teeth due to bleeding and gum swelling, a lot of soft dental plaque. Front teeth of lower jaw is covered with tartar. IG (Green-Vermillion) = 2.1. Clinical attachment is not lost. Loose teeth are not observed. PMA index = 19%; PI = 1.8.

Orthopantomogram: Bone tissue unchanged.

Diagnosis: Gingivitis caused by bacterial biofilm.

Microbiological study of insides of gingival sulcus identified: *Streptococcus intermedius* 5 × 10⁶ CFU/ml, *Streptococcus mitis* 10³ CFU/ml.

A fluorescent diagnostic device was used for diagnostics. It allows us to identify healthy, inflamed and atypical cells. The difference is color-coded.

Scaling and under gum treatment of pseudo-pockets, photodynamic therapy – 5 visits, every other day [12, 13].

Recommendation – complete oral hygiene, patient's motivation, 1 week course of inhalations with radonized Tskhaltubo water and using it as a mouthwash. Alpha rays of Radon in Tskhaltubo water plays a significant role in regulating inflammation and microflora and ultimately in maintaining homeostasis.

On the fifth day of the treatment, periodontal tissues were ameliorated. Unpleasant smell disappeared, gum bleeding was almost gone. After the course of the therapy, we observed relief in inflammation. After undergoing treatment and recommendation course, microbiological study observed the following: *Candida albicans* 3 × 10³ CFU/ml. PMA = 6%; PI = 0.3; SBI = 0.

Examinations to check the state were held according to the indicated period. After 3 months, the patient no longer had complaints, clinical signs of inflammation were not observed and did not need treatment. The patient continued maintenance therapy, examinations held after 6 and 12 months did not display deterioration, which was corroborated by clinical indices. 6 months later: OHI-S = 1.1; PMA = 9%; PI = 1.3; SBI = 1,1; 12 months later - OHI-S = 1.1; PMA = 9%; PI = 1.3; SBI = 1.1.

Pic.1

Standard clinical index dynamics in patient D. M. was positive after using antibacterial therapy for treating mild form of periodontitis. Thus, the obtained data points at long-term clinical effects of photodynamic therapy, Tskaltubo water Radon hormesis and microbiological study of the oral cavity.

The patient sticks with the rules of oral hygiene and occasionally uses recommended dose of inhalation of Tskaltubo radonized water.

Conclusion

Photosensitizer “Rada Dent”, device “Photodin-K” and inhalation of Radon in Tskaltubo water has combined effect. Through a non-invasive method used once in 6 months at the beginning and 1 or 2 years later, we managed to treat and prevent oral mucosa and periodontal disease without antibiotics. On the grounds of the treatment statistical data we can state that treatment of mild forms of periodontitis with the above mentioned combined method gives us a positive dynamics, which is reinforced with amelioration of clinical signs.

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PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND DISCOURSE MAKERS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

The paper tries to investigate the connection between AI and the people who make the discourse in English is a complicated one with many facets

The following objectives are set to achieve the aim of the paper:

1. Shed light on Ethics and the Use of Discourse Makers in English
2. Morals and new media

The methods of the research are quantitative and qualitative. Frequency analysis, discourse analysis, and other methods will be used to study our corpora.

Keywords: AI, DMs, NLP, Ethics, Morals, Media

Introduction

The connection between AI and the people who make the discourse in English is a complicated one with many facets. On the one hand, AI algorithms have the potential to be utilized in order to improve readability and enhance the efficiency of discourse creators in the English language. On the other side, the rising utilization of AI in the production of content raises problems regarding the authenticity and legitimacy of discourse makers.

Natural language processing (NLP) algorithms are one use of artificial intelligence that can be helpful to those who construct speech (Jones et al. 6). These algorithms can be applied to the analysis of text in order to locate places in which the readability of the text can be enhanced. For instance, you can use them to identify complicated language structures, an excessive amount of jargon, and other characteristics that can make it difficult to understand something. AI algorithms can assist discourse creators in producing content that is more approachable and engaging by identifying these challenges and providing solutions to them.

The aim of this paper is to:

1. Shed light on Ethics and the Use of Discourse Makers in English
2. Morals and new media

The employment of algorithms that generate content is another way that AI can be of assistance to those who are creating dialogue. These algorithms can be used to automatically generate material based on templates or rules that have been set in advance. For example, you can use them to produce headlines, summaries, or even whole articles with them. Discourse creators can save time and resources by automating these procedures, all while maintaining a consistent style and tone in their work. The growing use of AI in the production of content raises issues about the authenticity and legitimacy of those who generate discourse. It is becoming increasingly difficult to differentiate between information that was written by humans and content that was made by computers as AI algorithms continue to advance in their level of sophistication. Because of this, the readers' trust in the authors of the

discourse can be damaged, and the influence of their work can be lessened.

In addition to this, the implementation of AI in the production of material has the potential to increase preexisting prejudices and disparities. For instance, if AI algorithms are trained on data that displays prejudiced or discriminating ideas, then it is possible that such prejudices will be reproduced in the material that the algorithms generate. This can result in the continuation of harmful stereotypes as well as practices that exclude certain groups.

In spite of these issues, there is a substantial possibility that AI and the makers of discourse might collaborate in order to produce material that is of high quality, easily accessible, and that both engages and informs readers. Discourse makers are able to develop material that is more successful and influential than either human creativity or machine intelligence could achieve on their own by harnessing the capabilities of both of these factors in their work.

Ultimately, the interaction between AI and the creators of discourse in English is intricate and fraught with a variety of complexities. Concerns concerning authenticity, legitimacy, and bias have been raised in relation to artificial intelligence (AI), despite the fact that it has the potential to be a useful tool for strengthening the effectiveness of discourse producers and improving readability. As the field of artificial intelligence continues to advance, it will be essential for those who shape the discourse to give careful consideration to the part that technology plays in their work and to make certain that they uphold the highest possible standards of both quality and ethics.

1. Ethics and the Use of Discourse Makers in English

Discourse markers play such an important part in the process of creating and comprehending language, the use of them raises problems about morality. Linguists have a responsibility to consider the effects that discourse markers have on both individuals and communities, particularly when those discourse markers are used to uphold negative views or stereotypes. Dis-

course markers, such as the use of "uh" or "like" to imply that another person is unintelligent, are one example of how racial or gendered stereotypes can be reinforced through the use of language.

Linguists need to take into consideration a number of different factors, one of which is power relations in the deployment of discourse markers. The use of certain discourse markers might be misconstrued as an effort to dominate or exert control over the discussion, and this is especially true in circumstances in which one individual or group possesses a greater amount of social or cultural capital than another. This can generate sentiments of alienation and exclusion in persons who are not familiar with the meaning of the discourse markers in question or do not share those indicators themselves.

The manner in which discourse markers are utilised may also have an impact on the ethics of research. Researchers have a responsibility to ensure that they obtain the informed permission of participants and that they do nothing to jeopardise or harm people through the manipulation of language use. This is of utmost importance in studies involving minors as well as individuals whose cognitive or linguistic abilities are impaired, as participants in these types of studies may be more vulnerable or have less agency.

Linguists should use extreme caution when employing discourse markers and give serious consideration to the potential repercussions of doing so in light of the ethical concerns that have been raised. If researchers want to apply inclusive and respectful discourse markers that are aimed at empowering individuals and groups, they first need to be aware of the power dynamics that are at play in the use of language. When researchers find evidence that the use of particular discourse markers is contributing to the perpetuation of harmful attitudes or stereotypes, they should work to question dominant narratives and advance more inclusive and equitable modes of communication. In addition, they should work to advance more inclusive and equitable modes of communication.

2. Morals and new media

When utilised in modern media such as social networks, online discussion boards, and electronic discourse, discourse markers give rise to new ethical problems. The use of emoticons, hashtags, and acronyms are all examples of discourse markers, and they have a significant impact on online communication. Yet, there may be ethical problems with its implementation because there are difficulties of veracity, exclusion, and secrecy.

When it comes to ethical considerations, accuracy is of the utmost importance when employing discourse

markers in digital media. In written or electronic communication, discourse markers are used frequently to express the attitude or feeling of the speaker. Yet, the participants' cultural backgrounds as well as the surrounding surroundings may cause some difference in how they interpret these signals. Failure to correctly perceive or communicate discourse markers can lead to a variety of problems, including disagreements, misunderstandings, and the spread of incorrect information. Users of digital platforms have an obligation to consider the likelihood of misunderstandings and strive for greater specificity in their use of discourse markers in order to increase the likelihood that their communications will be understood in the manner in which they were intended.

When it comes to ethical considerations involving the utilisation of discourse markers in new media, inclusion should take precedence. Depending on the discourse markers that are utilised, the manner in which people communicate with one another online may either be more or less inviting of individuals from a variety of backgrounds and points of view. When certain speech indicators are utilised, it is possible for individuals who come from a variety of racial, ethnic, religious, linguistic, or socioeconomic backgrounds to be excluded from dialogues. Users of new media have a responsibility to be aware of the implications of excluding people and to make concerted efforts to incorporate them into the discussions they have with others by employing a wide range of inclusive discourse markers in their writing and in their spoken communication.

The use of discourse markers in new media raises moral concerns regarding the invasion of personal space. When the usage of discourse markers such as hashtags and location identifiers reveals the whereabouts and activities of persons, there is a justifiable basis for concerns pertaining to privacy and security. Users of new media should be aware of the potential risks to their privacy that are linked with the use of discourse markers, and they should take the appropriate safeguards to protect not just their own personal information but also the personal information of others.

The utilization of discourse markers in contemporary media gives rise to additional worries relating to the gathering of data and the processing of algorithms. When algorithms use discourse markers for data analysis, sentiment analysis, or content suggestion, ethical considerations around data privacy, permission, and algorithmic biases occur. When using discourse markers, consumers of modern media would be well to give some thought to the context of data collection and algorithmic processing.

Table 1

Ethical Considerations	News Media	Entertainment Media
Accuracy	The data, facts, and events that are presented by the discourse markers in the news media ought to be presented in an open and honest manner. Misunderstandings, prejudice, and disagreements are all potential outcomes of incorrectly using or interpreting discourse markers in a conversation.	Congruence is required to exist between the discourse markers used in a piece of entertainment media and the tone, mood, and genre that are intended to be conveyed by the work. The improper or careless use of discourse markers can lead to a variety of problematic outcomes, including misrepresentation, stereotyping, and cultural appropriation.
Inclusivity	Language markers should be used by media sources in a way that is both open to and respectful of the diverse identities, cultures, and points of view that exist in the world. Reporters have a responsibility to avoid employing speech markers that can be construed in a way that is discriminatory or exclusive if they want to promote diversity and inclusion in the news.	It is important for those working in the entertainment sector to be aware of the consequences of the discourse markers they use. It is necessary to abstain from using language that is cruel, discriminatory, or insulting if one wishes to encourage acceptance and understanding of the many different groups and identities that exist.
Privacy	The identification of individuals, their locations, or the activities they are engaged in should not be divulged through the use of discourse markers in the media because this could put them in danger. While reporting the news, discourse markers should be utilised with caution to safeguard people's privacy and avoid betraying their faith in the media.	It is of the utmost importance that, in this day and age of social media and online interactions, entertainment media refrain from using discourse markers that may put users' privacy at risk or do not have their consent. In today's popular culture, the utilisation of discourse markers is always required to be carried out with the person's knowledge and permission.
Data Processing	Discourse markers are often used in the news media, and algorithms could process these markers to do data analysis, sentiment analysis, and content suggestion. Protecting the privacy of users of discourse markers, gaining informed consent, and addressing the possibility for algorithmic prejudice are all important ethical factors that should be taken into account when using discourse markers in the media.	Processing discourse markers used in entertainment media can also be done by algorithms, which can then be used to make content recommendations, create user profiles, or show targeted adverts. When it comes to the use of discourse markers in forms of entertainment media, there are a variety of moral considerations that need to be taken into account.

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SOCIAL SCIENCES

DESTRUCTIVENESS AND DESTRUCTOLOGY

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ДЕСТРУКТИВНОСТЬ И ДЕСТРУКТОЛОГИЯ

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Abstract

Destructology was announced as a new independent scientific discipline. However, in this form it does not meet the requirements of scientific rationality. The currently publicly presented destructology could be considered a compendium of recommendations for individuals wary of a destructive situation.

Аннотация

Деструктология была объявлена как новая самостоятельная научная дисциплина. Однако в указанном виде она не отвечает требованиям научной рациональности. Публично представленную в настоящее время деструктологию можно считать сборником рекомендаций для лиц, остерегающихся деструктивной ситуации.

Keywords: destructiveness, destructology, conflictology, sectology, science, scientific rationality.

Ключевые слова: деструктивность, деструктология, конфликтология, сектология, наука, научная рациональность.

В последнее время появилось значительное количество публикаций (статей и учебных пособий, издан также учебник коллектива авторов), посвященных тем вопросам, которые могут быть отнесены к деструктивным проявлениям во взаимодействии между людьми. Более того, высказано мнение о создании новой науки под названием «деструктология» или «деструктоведение» (*лат.* destructio, deconstructio - разложение, разрушение; logos - наука). Поэтому имеет смысл рассмотреть отдельные термины и понятия, связанные с данной проблемой.

Деструктивность на практике выражается в неких действиях личности, направленных на разрушение определенной структуры, сложившейся во внешней среде или в самой личности. Деструктивность может проявиться в том, что человек необоснованно стремится к получению быстрого результата без анализа возможных последствий своих действий, оказывается неспособным к рациональной реакции на возникшие условия, что вызывает девиантное поведение.

Проблемами деструктивности занимались многие психологи прошлого. К примеру, Зигмунд Фрейд считал, что деструктивность той или иной направленности присуща любой личности; а Эрих Фромм утверждал, что деструктивность личности возникает лишь при определенных случаях. Э.Фромм выделял два вида деструктивности: доб-

рокачественную (оборонительную, служащую психологической защитой) и злокачественную (необоснованную, чаще всего связанную с жестокостью). Современные исследователи считают, что деструктивностью в определенной степени обладает каждый человек, она проявляется как стремление к ощущению комфортных условий (в понимании этого человека) собственной жизнедеятельности, и не всегда представляет собой своеобразный механизм психологической защиты. В психологии она понимается как личностное свойство, характеризующееся негативным отношением к себе или к другим людям. Основными причинами человеческой деструктивности принято считать невозможность самореализации, конформизм, изолированность и одиночество, нарциссизм, неуверенность в себе, комплекс неполноценности, ощущение собственной незначительности, безразличия или презрения со стороны окружающих, скуку, пассивность, депрессию.

Деструктивное поведение личности, несомненно, создает конфликтную ситуацию в общении. О наличии конфликтов среди людей известно давно, начиная с глубокой древности, но научный интерес к этому явлению сформировался лишь к концу XIX века. В настоящее время выработано немалое число общепризнанных определений конфликта с позиции различных научных направлений. К примеру, конфликт- это:

- естественное условие взаимодействия людей, в основе которого лежат противоречия, существенные различия между интересами и ценностями субъектов социальных связей; будучи проявлением общения существ, способных к самосознанию, конфликт означает отсутствие согласия, расхождение во мнениях, столкновение разных взглядов и желаний, противоположных при данных обстоятельствах тенденций, потребностей, интересов, мотивов и стилей поведения (в психологии);

- предельное обострение противоречий, столкновение и противоборство, вызываемые противоположностью, несовместимостью интересов и позиций личностей, групп и т.п. (в социологии);

- противоборство субъектов (носителей) противоречий, противодействие сторон, преследующих несовпадающие или взаимно исключающие друг друга цели (в юриспруденции);

- универсальный способ взаимодействия сложных систем, преодоления противоречий и ограничений в любой сфере, где осуществляются контакты между отдельными людьми и их сообществами (в теории управления);

- социальное явление, нормальное проявление социальных связей и отношений между людьми, способ взаимодействия людей при столкновении их несовместимых взглядов, позиций и интересов, противоборство взаимосвязанных, но преследующих свои цели двух или более сторон (в конфликтологии) и т.д. [1, с.35-36].

Наука конфликтология, как область научного знания о природе, причинах, видах и динамике конфликтов, методах их предупреждения и способах разрешения, пользуется общим признанием. В ней указывается, что в основе любого конфликта лежит ситуация, включающая либо противоречивые позиции сторон по какому-либо поводу, либо противоположные цели или средства их достижения в данных обстоятельствах, либо несовпадение интересов, желаний, оппонентов и т.п. При этом конструктивный конфликт характеризуется своим позитивным влиянием на структуру, динамику и результативность социально-психологических и организационных процессов, служащих источником самоусовершенствования и саморазвития личности и группы [1, с.224]. При иных характеристиках конфликт следует признать неконструктивным (непродуктивным, негативным, деструктивным).

Таким образом, конфликт - это противоречия и столкновения людей из-за несовместимости интересов участников процесса взаимодействия. Поскольку люди не могут быть одинаковыми во всем, то их интересы также не могут быть полностью совпадающими во все времена и на любом пространстве, в любых условиях. Как указано выше, конфликты между людьми могут быть позитивными (конструктивными) или негативными (деструктивными). Поэтому противоречия деструктивного характера могут быть отнесены именно к области рассмотрения конфликтологии вполне обоснованно.

Однако отсюда не следует, что какое-либо направление самой науки конфликтологии не мо-

жет быть скомпоновано и объявлено как новая самостоятельная научная отрасль. Достаточно вспомнить историю науки, которая изобилует примерами того, как по мере развития и обогащения некоей науки были сформированы и выделены новые самостоятельные научные отрасли. В то же время следует учитывать, что формирование нового научного направления и его признание связаны с определенным множеством требований и соответствующих условий.

Для дальнейших рассуждений по рассматриваемой проблеме необходимо обратиться, прежде всего, к понятию «наука». Известно, что наука определяется как «когнитивная и практическая деятельность по производству, обоснованию и применению научного знания». Научным же называют знание, «отвечающее принятым в науке требованиям научной рациональности». Любое научное знание, независимо от его формы и содержания должно соответствовать общим (рациональным) требованиям научной рациональности: «объектная предметность, однозначность понятий, высказываний и операций, эмпирическая и теоретическая обоснованность, логическая системность, рефлексивность, методологичность, открытость к критике и изменениям, возможность совершенствования, практическая полезность» [2, с.55, 62]. Легко видеть, что деструктология в том виде, в каком её представляют публично, не отвечает указанному списку требований. Например, можно обратиться к требованию обоснованности. В научных исследованиях следует учитывать принцип достаточного основания, т.е. истинность или ложность утверждения может быть обосновано лишь ответом на вопрос: «Почему именно дело обстоит так, а не иначе?» (Г.Лейбниц).

Следует учитывать и то обстоятельство, что любое научное знание само по себе нейтрально по отношению к властным структурам. Это выражается и в том, что определенное научное знание может служить как для повышения благосостояния людей, так и в разрушительных целях. Атомная энергия, к примеру, служит людям в атомных электростанциях, а также используется в создании т.н. атомной бомбы. Заметим, что подобное свойство науки известно и основателю деструктологии. Он подчеркивает наличие двух противоположных тенденций в современном гуманитарном пространстве: «созидательной, которая направлена на реализацию межкультурного и межрелигиозного диалога между представителями различных культур, и разрушительной, которая направлена на использование внешних, внутренних, религиозных, политических и иных ресурсов для формирования конфликтогенных зон» [4, с.262].

Однако представленная деструктология сама может быть оценена лишь как «одномерное» рассуждение, не связанное с научными открытиями. В самом деле, никакая наука не может ставить целью поддержать какую-либо власть (наука открывает объективную истину независимо от того, насколько эта истина может быть полезной для данной госу-

дарственной власти). Однако деструктология пред- назначена особая роль: её целью является «Повы- сить уровень национальной безопасности и мини- мизировать вовлечение граждан в деструктивные организации» [5]. Значит, заранее объявлено, что нововведение будет служить благополучию именно данной власти в данный период существования конкретного государства. Ведь сложившаяся ситу- ация ставит перед силами национальной безопас- ности России «задачу разработки комплекса мер, при- менение которых позволит предотвратить реальные опасности не только для отдельных групп населения, но и для целых этнокультурных сообществ» [4, с.263]. Поэтому здесь можно говорить лишь о сбор- нике рекомендаций для граждан данного государ- ства в данный период, но не о научном направле- нии.

Трудно согласиться также с определением объекта и предмета новой науки. Объектом «де- структологии выступает совокупность деструктив- ных новообразований (организаций, групп, контр- культур, игровых увлечений и пр.). При этом указан- ная совокупность носит гетерогенный характер». Её предметом «являются причины, закономерности возникновения, признаки, модификации и особен- ности функционирования деструктивных новообра- зований, их проявления в жизни общества и взаимо- связи между ними... Деструктология, равно как и конфликтология, изучает конфликтогенные фак- торы, однако деструктологию интересуют прежде всего последствия, вызванные развитием и эскала- цией различных видов конфликта» [4, с.266, 267].

Значит, в сфере новой науки входят лишь но- вообразования, т.е. здесь не принимаются во вни- мание уже известные, сложившиеся объединения и организации. Таким же образом отбрасываются го- могенные совокупности, поскольку подчеркнут ге- терогенный характер изучаемых объединений. Ве- роятно, подразумевается, что «высокопоставлен- ные деструктологи» в каждом конкретном случае должны будут объяснить, куда относить то или иное объединение. Кроме того, ещё окажется необ- ходимым «запретить» конфликтологам исследо- вать какие-либо последствия любого конфликта, т.к. это уже отнесено к сфере новой науки деструк- тологии.

При этом считается необходимой подготовка «специалистов нового профиля, одинаково хорошо разбирающихся как в противодействии терроризму, так и в опасных молодежных субкультурах». Указы- вается, что именно лишь такие специалисты спо- собны противостоять деятельности некоторых объ- единений деструктивного характера, которые могут иметь «черты политического движения, религиоз- ной секты и организованной преступной группир- овки, что придает ей гибридный характер и обеспе- чивает присутствие в различных типах сред». А это, оказывается, требует «институционализации новой прикладной научной дисциплины -деструктоло- гии... Данная дисциплина позволит объединить компетенции религиоведов (особенно исламоведов и сектоведов), специализирующихся на работе с

трудными подростками педагогов, психологов, куль- турологов, лингвистов и специалистов по информа- ционной безопасности». Далее указывается, что «Помимо общего набора компетенций деструктоло- гам необходимы знания из области психологии, юриспруденции, культурологии, рекламы, меди- цины, в том числе физиологии и психиатрии. Ука- занный перечень не является полным» [4, с.264,268].

Легко видеть, что совокупность перечислен- ных качеств представляет собой общие требования к современному работнику, деятельность которого связана с межличностным общением. Подобные разносторонне подготовленные специалисты нашли бы свое место не только в деструктологии, но и в любом виде современной трудовой деятельности; предусмотренные здесь требования к специали- стам- «деструктологам», являются неперенными условиями успешной деятельности чуть ли не всех представителей современных профессий. Взять, к примеру, школьного учителя: он должен владеть основами психолого- педагогических наук, культу- рологии и социологии, лингвистики и информа- тики. Ко всему почему, он обязан хорошо знать осо- бенности обучения и воспитания школьников в раз- личные возрастные периоды. Стало быть, выпускник педагогического вуза уже соответствует уровню деструктолога с точки зрения реализации вышеприведенных требований. Более того, можно указать и другие современные профессии, преду- сматривающие владение компетенциями, перечис- ленными выше.

Стало быть, эти требования сами по себе явля- ются общими, предназначенными для современ- ного работника, а не частными, которым должен удовлетворять «новый специалист-деструктолог». В то же время вышеуказанные рассуждения не мо- гут служить основанием для формирования новой науки. Как и было указано, они могут служить ре- комендациями для сотрудников правоохранитель- ных органов страны.

Основателю данного нововведения известно, что уже существуют новые отрасли, занятые реше- нием проблем, которые предполагалось относить к сфере деструктологии. К примеру, более чем сто лет тому назад в России возникла дисциплина сектове- дение (сектология), которая занимается изучением сект, культов, псевдорелигиозных обществ и т.д. Сектология получила признание научной обще- ственности как самостоятельная отрасль науки. Проб- лемы дальнейшего развития сектологии и её прак- тического применения были рассмотрены на Межд- ународной конференции, проведенной в Нижнем Новгороде (РФ, 2001 год). В 2014 году была издана объемная (816 страниц) книга А.Л.Дворкина «Секто- ведение. Тоталитарные секты: опыт систематиче- ского исследования». Указанное - третье издание книги содержит результаты многолетних скрупулёз- ных исследований. Здесь рассмотрены секты-долго- жители, поствоенная эклектика, псевдотиндуист- ские и псевдобиблейские секты, постсоветская эк- лектика и т.д. О широте исследованных проблем можно судить даже по тому, что в третьем издании

книги научному анализу подвергнута деятельность более двух десятков различных сект и объединений, в т.ч. таких, как мормоны, иеговисты, сайентологи-сты, неодесятники, «ивановцы», современный индуизм и гуруистские секты, «Общество сознания Кришны», «Движение объединения» Сан Мен Муна, «Трансцендентальная медитация», «Белое братство», Движение «Нью эйдж» и т.д. Короче говоря, сектология признана как наука, пользуется широким набором объектов исследования и продолжает развиваться. В настоящее время не представляется рациональным отделение некоторой части этой науки как самостоятельной отрасли.

Выше уже указывалось, что проблемы деструктологии относятся также к сфере конфликтологии. Кроме того, объявлено также об отпочковании т.н. террологии, которая определена как автономная научная дисциплина, динамично развивающаяся «на стыке философии, политологии и социологии, конфликтологии, криминалистики и других наук за рубежом и в России». Указывается, что основные подходы террологии «связаны с объяснением и пониманием причин, роли террористического насилия в современном мире как искусственно создаваемого пространства страха для достижения различных политических, экономических, социальных и духовных целей, структурированного многообразными и взаимосвязанными социальными субъектами» (В.В.Кафтан). Известно также о попытках формировать такие самостоятельные научные отрасли как диссидентология, оперативно - розыскная террология и т.п.

При рассмотрении подобных явлений может сложиться мнение, что это подтверждает тезис о бурном развитии гуманитарных наук. В самом деле, известно, что люди неодинаковы, любая личность характеризуется разнообразной совокупностью тех или иных, индивидуальных и общественно значимых качеств. «Нет человека, состоящего из одних достоинств, не имеющего какого-либо изъяна или слабостей... Нельзя не считаться с фактом того, что поведение любого человека, его действия и поступки опосредуют реакцию личности на ту или иную жизненную ситуацию, выражают свойственные ей как рациональные, так и эмоциональные качества, те или иные склонности, взгляды, мотивы» [1, с.55]. Стало быть, существуют неограниченные возможности для формирования бесконечного числа разнообразных научных направлений.

Однако подобное измельчение без достаточных научных обоснований не может служить показателем развития самой науки. Не все её отдельные части достигают необходимого уровня развития, разработанности и обоснования, чтобы иметь возможность существовать самостоятельно и получить необходимое признание. Более того, необоснованное выделение тех или иных частей какой-либо науки может нарушить её целостность. Поэтому даже для убежденных сторонников дальнейшего научного развития и связанного с этим развитием возникновения новых научных отраслей, проблема формирования самостоятельного научного направления требует разностороннего, необходимого обоснования. При

этом следовало бы и ответить на вопрос о том, что будет с основной наукой, от которой «отрываются» отдельные кусочки, неспособные существовать и развиваться вне данной науки. Стало быть, формирование новой научной дисциплины требует не только и не столько стремления какой бы то личности стать основателем новой науки. Необходимо решение значительного комплекса проблем, которые могли бы стать базой обоснования для публичного объявления о новой науке.

Вышеприведенные высказывания не позволяют утверждать в настоящее время о создании новой науки деструктологии. Поэтому не могут быть признаны научными те выводы, которые представляются от имени этой «науки». Однако в современной российской практике имеются примеры того, что некоторые утверждения от имени деструктологии принимаются как научные доказательства. К примеру, можно сослаться на обвинения, послужившие основой для лишения свободы автора пьесы «Финист Ясный Сокол» и режиссера театральной постановки. По содержанию спектакля у кого-то создалось впечатление, что даже в ИГИЛе лучше, чем в России (ИГИЛ-террористическая организация, запрещенная в РФ). Р.А.Силантьев посчитал это опасным явлением и пропагандой терроризма. «Поэтому,- подчеркивает он,- эти вещи недопустимы. Особенно когда за это театральные премии дают, когда это пиарится, и даже когда это, простите, люди еврейской национальности делают. Я уже не первый раз наблюдаю, что евреи активно за ваххабитов выступают, такое ощущение, что назло русским... Это безобразно надо прекратить» [3]. Очевидно, невозможно называть научным подобное утверждение, когда абсолютно не допускается чье-либо преимущество над Россией и русским народом. К слову, он не случайно вспомнил здесь и ваххабитов. В одной из своих речей в 2016 году он однозначно требовал убивать ваххабитов: «Необходимо резко ужесточить законодательство и перестать думать о том, что мирным путем и договорами можно что-то решить. Надо просто их уничтожить. Как мы убивали фашистов, так надо убивать и ваххабитов» [5]. При подобных взглядах автора трудно найти научную объективность в каких-либо его экспертизах.

В 2020 году издана книга Силантьева Р.А. и Чекмаева С.В. «Деструктология. Как быстро и надежно лишиться денег и здоровья. 10 шагов к успеху». (М.: изд. «Пятый Рим»). В предисловии к книге авторы охарактеризовали деструктологию как сборник советов и рекомендаций: «Как минимизировать все риски в этой трагикомической сфере и учит молодая наука деструктология... Так что считайте эту книгу инструкцией по технике духовной безопасности. Как не попасть туда, куда не надо, да и за другими присмотреть». Заметим, что, деструктология учит, оказывается, ещё и тому, как за другими людьми присматривать.

Складывается впечатление, что основатель деструктологии понимает науку весьма своеобразно, как о некоей помощнице действующей власти, призванной лишь подтверждать высокий научный ста-

тус любого утверждения вышестоящих лиц. В упомянутой книге утверждается также: «Что есть религия, а что есть атеизм, ученые спорят веками и будут спорить до скончания времен. В России первый вопрос, правда, успешно решен – с 2009 года его определяет Экспертный совет по государственной религиоведческой экспертизе при Минюсте РФ. С атеизмом сложнее». Стало быть, любые научные утверждения могут быть заменены указаниями каких-либо официальных органов власти. Оказывается, достаточно создать какой-нибудь экспертный совет с правом решения спорных вопросов. В этом случае нужда в науке отпадает полностью, тогда любое утверждение официального учреждения считается научной. Очевидно, именно такое положение составляет суть авторитарной власти и полностью исключает всякую науку.

В заключение подчеркнем, что в данной работе не поставлена цель раскрывать какие-либо особенности взглядов основателя деструктологии. Наша цель заключалась лишь в стремлении понять степень научной обоснованности имеющегося материала. На основе проведенного анализа можно утвер-

ждать, что существующие в настоящее время материалы не позволяют признавать деструктологию как самостоятельную научную отрасль.

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